

SPECIFIC FORMS AND FEATURES OF SPEECH CULTURE

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Abstract. *In this article the main attention is paid to specific forms and peculiarities of the culture of speech in human communication, as well as questions of the oral form of speech, spoken and written language. Live spoken language also has its own lexical, grammatical and other features. Each form of literary speech has its own lexical, grammatical and other characteristics, these issues are covered in detail in this article.*

Keywords: *human relations, speech types, forms, oral and written speech, literary language rules, eloquence, grammar, vocabulary words, press speech, radio and sarcasm, antithesis, slang, speech art.*

INTRODUCTION

People express their inner experiences, dreams, and expectations in the process of communicating and speaking. In the **introductory** part of the article, an attempt is made to reveal that the development of society for the sake of people, and the formation of relations between people with each other in general is impossible to imagine without mutual communication and cooperation. Communication and speech - an important form of interaction, showing the inner and outer world of man. In the process of communication, a person expresses his views, representations, and feelings about the external world, the way of life of society, and his social, economic, and spiritual life. All this is reflected in the culture of speech and has its forms and features.

If we focus on the **theoretical aspects** of the article, then, first of all, with the change in social relations and living conditions of members of society, their imagination, ideas, worldviews, manners and moral norms about the material world will also change. Such a change takes place based on common interests and goodwill of people. With the advent of human society, the need for communication between people was felt. The interaction of the members of the society with each other has become the basis for the comprehensive development of this society. The importance of knowledge of speech forms in the study of the science of "oratory and the culture of speech" is incomparable. Linguists distinguish forms of speech as oral speech and written speech. Some scientists attribute colloquial speech to them. Because, according to experts, the most common form of speech is spoken language. The oral form of speech is widespread. It seems easy to many. In fact, oral speech is very important to attract the attention of the audience. The main feature of oral speech is that thoughts, words, expressions often appear when the speaker speaks from the pulpit, depending on the situation. The speaker should always be ready to give a lecture on an interesting, fascinating topic.

As a result, we will pay attention to the **practical aspects** of the article and comment on certain forms of speech: **Oral speech form:**

The first form of **oral speech** is a lecture. The speaker prepares his speech in writing but speaks only orally. The speaker must know where, to whom, how much and how to speak. Voice plays a key role in speech. Performance skills are of great importance in the lecture, i.e., in

conveying the collected material to the audience. Even the best speaker is worthless without execution.

When Demosthenes was asked, “What is most important in being announcer?” he replied, “The first is performance, the second is performance, the third is performance”. The performance in a lecture, that is, the delivery of thoughts, ideas to the listener, is done with the help of a pleasant voice.

The second form of oral speech is conversation. “Each speech is composed of content and words, and in each speech, without content, the words lose their ground, and the content without words loses its clarity”. So, conversation means the exchange of ideas between two people or several people. Every intelligent person should be ready for any conversation. The conversation has its rules. When an elderly person speaks, young people should not interrupt him until he is finished talking. When talking it is necessary to be very careful with every word, speech, and thought, to respect the interlocutor, and observe the rules of etiquette even when reacting. As far as possible, interlocutors should try to make a good impression on each other. Conversations are of two types. Specially prepared interviews or off-site interviews. Questions for television, radio, newspapers, and magazines are prepared and given to the interlocutor in advance. The second type of conversation is the conversation that takes place sitting next to the train, or bus, at weddings, maracas, and meetings.

Regardless of where, when, and between what gender conversations take place, interlocutors must learn to respect each other and speak face to face. The peculiarity of oral speech is that speech is in the form of live colloquial speech, so sentences should be very short and simple. Another form of communication is discussion. The term “discussion” refers to a round-table discussion of 30-40 mature professionals involved in the field, with the participation of 30-40 people, which are usually organized in the family, in the neighborhood and in public places. Unfortunately, in most cases, speakers and interlocutors talk without speaking, rush to react, try to express a new thought, speak out of turn or talk long.

Oral lectures are widely used in schools, high schools, colleges, institutes and universities. The lecture can last 15, 25, 35, 45, 60 minutes as a teacher. The speaker needs to prepare very carefully for each lecture, tell the audience, whether he is a student or a student, a new idea, a new phrase, something new. The speaker should pay attention to the age of the audience. The forms of speech include such forms as book speech, literary speech, tank speech, welcoming speech, advertising speech, speech, information speech.

Another form of speech is **written speech**. In written speech, the thought must be clear and impressive. The subject or information to be given in a written speech is well written and coherent. A disadvantage of written speech compared to oral is that some errors in oral speech are not noticed, and in written speech there are mistakes “here I”, regardless of whether they are spelling, stylistic or in any other form. In written speech, the speaker must first know the Uzbek literary language, spelling dictionary, grammar of the Uzbek language, spelling rules, syllabic translation, punctuation. Today, most of our youth are not at the required level of literacy. Probably, hence the saying: “You are satisfied with what you say, you are not satisfied with what you write”.

According to expert scientists, there are also types of written speech, such as lecture, synopsis, abstract, independent work, review, recommendation letter, description, statement, resume.

Another form of speech is colloquial speech, which is a form of oral speech. Listening plays a key role in conversational speech.

Live spoken speech also has its own lexical, grammatical and other features. According to some researchers, live conversational speech is determined as if it contradicts the written form of scientific, official, journalistic and artistic methods strictly adhering to the literary language. Live spoken speech is defined as a separate form of speech, and written speech styles (scientific, official, journalistic, artistic) following the literary language are defined as separate speech forms. Live spoken speech is characterized by randomness (impromptu). Also, this type of speech is usually in the form of dialogic speech. Slang can be allowed in it. It has its own lexical units (*aylanay, o'rgilay, jonginam, bo'pti, mayli, xo'p, bo'laveradi, yo'g'-ye, opke, kelaver ...* etc.). In live conversational speech, the words are widely used:

Many features of live speech are expressed in these passages. Each form of literary speech has its own lexical, grammatical, etc. features, as well as such forms as scientific style, formal style, artistic style.

Forms of literary speech. “Language is the “key” of the heart”. “A good word is the master of the heart.” Since language is multifaceted and complex, it is also studied by the science of linguistics. It has such departments as phonetics, lexicology, grammar, morphology, and syntax. People use tools other than language to communicate and think. But the main place in the growth of speech is literary speech. The subjection of language to certain norms and rules is called literary language. Literary language has written and oral forms. The written form of literary language is based on figurative means and is subject to the rules of correct writing and is called **orthography** (spelling). The oral form of literary language is based on such means as speech sounds, intonation, accent. Orthography studies the rules of pronunciation.

The scientific and methodical view of the literary language is of great importance in the system of higher education. Scientific speech is the speech of scientific works, that is, it is in the form of scientific articles, scientific brochures, textbooks, monographs, teaching aids, dissertations, scientific lectures.

It is noted that there are two types of official speech:

1. Oral statements by the official speakers.
2. Official working speech (written). Written application for employment, written notice of leave, receipt or order - all this is typical for an official written speech. If the speaker speaks in a formal language in front of the leaders, he speaks in a formal, pre-written text - in a formal style. The speech of the official lectures in the oral style differs from the speech of artistic, scientific, lively spoken, journalistic, and differs from the speech of official working papers. Fiction is a means of educating young people and developing human speech.

Also, by reading stories, novels, stories, poems and epics of many talented writers, poets, he improves his knowledge, enriches his language, learns to express his opinion correctly, clearly and clearly in talks and lectures. There are different forms and ways of using literature in speech. Depending on where and with whom he is talking or giving a lecture, the speaker can use artistic imagery, quote excerpts from works, read poetry.

Although the speaker is giving a talk on the international situation among 60-70-year-olds, it is certainly not acceptable if he is reading a poem about love. Because he needs to know when and where to use fiction with his intellect. Reading excerpts from works of art should serve to enrich the speech and improve the mood of the listeners. The value of examples of popular oral

literature in enriching a speaker's speech is incomparable. Every orator should increase his vocabulary, using proverbs popular in the people, not popular in the people, the wise words of scientists. The role of fiction in the development of speech is great. In fiction there is also author's speech. This is a component of the language of a work of fiction, in which the author's statement and comments are expressed in the language of the narrator, different from the speech of the characters. Character speech is the speech of additional characters that manifests and complements the characteristics of the hero of the work. It expresses his thoughts and feelings, attitude towards life events.

Reported speech is to copy what others have said while retaining meaning. If the speech of the characters of the artwork is borrowed from others and is pronounced by comparison, it is called assigned speech.

A **monologue** is a speech addressed to oneself or other participants in a work of art. Monological speech differs from dialogical speech in that it does not involve other persons.

In addition to the author's speech and the speech of the characters, there is also fiction speech in fiction. The speaker should pay attention and study the variety and abundance of images in fiction, what the writer, the poet wants to say with his work, what means of imagery he uses in his speech in words and phrases. Elements of a literary work, creating scenes and images that can be seen, heard, felt and felt, are called visual aids. Figurative means are the techniques of artistic representation of reality, pictorial and emotional means, and such their manifestations as animation, clarification, comparison, exaggeration, antithesis, sarcasm, figurative parallelism, symbolic images, allegorical images are often found in folklore and written literature.

Like any poet, the speaker is also the creator. In his speech, the speaker will be able to quote excerpts from the works of beloved and famous poets and writers and give examples. Exaggeration adorns the speaker's speech, increases the impact, attracts the attention of the audience.

Antithesis means the opposite. The speaker provides a better understanding of the event by taking contrast in his speech.

Sarcasm is one of the techniques of disclosure in more critical speech, satirical works: it consists of bitter poison, sarcastic rebukes and insults.

In his speech, the speaker should, if possible, not use dialects, local words (dialectisms) found in works of fiction. Because the speaker's speech should be understandable to all present. Besides them, there are words and word combinations used only in certain places, villages, cities, districts, which in linguistics are called **provincialisms**. Also, words related to a profession are called professionalism. The terms jargonism, barbarism and ideology are also found in the Uzbek language.

Jargon, that is, words and expressions that appeared in a certain environment, used by merchants and thieves. Words that appear on the demand of the time are called **ideologies**. Therefore, the speaker must be able to use the various innovations of language in expanding his or her speech.

As mentioned above, the speaker should know the grammar, syntax and phonetics of the Uzbek language perfectly. Scientific speech is a philosophical speech, journalistic speeches are devoid of artistry and emotionality, but have strong logic.

Intonation is the main means of expressiveness, that is, the attitude of the speaker to the interlocutor, and helps to express the meaning expected from the speech of the speaker, to revive

the speech. In speech, the speaker is used to express thoughts and feelings such as question, exclamation, sign, sarcasm, anger, stress. Every speaker can skillfully use the wise words, proverbs and sayings of Central Asian and world thinkers. If he quotes and uses passages from songs, fairy tales, poems in his speech, it proves the speaker's skill.

Correct word pronunciation and intonation play an important role in **speech etiquette**. In the Uzbek language, the stress usually falls on the last syllable of a word. If the speaker pays special attention to the stress of each word, he or she can know that the level of content and effectiveness of his or her speech will increase. One of the most important signs of speaking is the intonation of the spoken sentence. If a speaker's speech continues at the same pace, in the same voice, no matter how important, relevant, and interesting the ideas are, listeners, especially students, will get bored and will not accept any ideas or anything. Experienced speakers pay special attention to increasing the meaningfulness of speech through rhythmic and melodic structure of speech, changes in pitch, volume, and sound vibration.

Uzbek speech has its components such as intonation, silence, tempo, rhythm. In preparing to speak, the speaker should determine where the tone and pause would lie. All forms of art help the speaker to strengthen his speech. The speaker should read and study scientific works.

CONCLUSION

So, we can **conclude** that the speaker should be able to understand what digital economy is and be able to explain it to the general public. Nowadays it is said that it is necessary to promote the production of innovations and discoveries in science on the initiative of the President, to serve the development of the country. So, the speaker must keep up with the times. The person who wants to become a speaker must first master the Uzbek language.

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